

About distribution, host plant and habitat preferences of the Alydidae (Hemiptera, Heteroptera) species of Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: In this study, some habitats, host plants, altitude and distribution information of 8 species belonging to five genera of Türkiye Alydidae (Hemiptera.Heteroptera) species are given.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, Alydidae, host plants, altitude, distribution, Türkiye.

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INTRODUCTION

Terrestrial heteropteran species have different habitat and feeding preferences, just as Alydidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) species have habitat preferences and phytophagous feeding preferences, and their relationships with plants also vary.

Alydidae is a family belonging to the Heteroptera suborder, which has about 50 genera and 200 species worldwide. In the Palaearctic Region; 69 species

belonging to 26 genera have been identified (Dolling, 2006).

In Turkey, 7 species belonging to five genera have been recorded so far. Since 1864, records of Turkey's Alydidae family have been included in the literature. There are studies on Alydidae family species in Turkey: Fieber, 1864; Horváth, 1901; Fahringer, 1922; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Hoberlandt 1955; Seidenstücker 1957; Linnavuori, 1965; Wagner, 1966; Tuatay et al.,

1972; Ural et al., 1973; Altınayar, 1981; Horváth, 1899, *Camptopus lateralis* Pehlivan, 1981; Zümreoğlu & Akbulut, (Germar, 1817), *Camptopus tragacanthae* (Kolenati, 1845), *Heegeria tangirica* (Saunders, 1877); *Megalotomus ornaticeps* (Stål, 1858), *Namausus sordidatus* (Stål, 1858).
 1987; Kıyak, 1990a, b, 1993; Çağlar, 1992; Önder et al, 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun, et al., 2010; Çerçi et al., 2016; Çerçi & Koçak, 2017; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021.

As a result of these studies, *Alydus calcaratus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Camptopus bifasciatus* Fieber, 1864, *Camptopus illustris*

These studies on Turkey are reviewed and the habitats, host plant preferences, altitude and distribution information of 8 species belonging to five genera of Turkey Alydidae are given below.

RESULTS

Hemiptera Linnaeus, 1758

Heteroptera Latreille, 1810

Family ALYDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily ALYDINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Heegeria Reuter, 1881

Heegeria tangirica (Saunders, 1877)

Habitat and hostplant: It is reported to live in Fabaceae (Carapezza & Mifsud, 2015). It was collected on a rock in Turkey. (Çerçi & Koçak, 2017).

Distribution in Turkey: İzmir: Çeşme, Ildırı; Muğla: Bodrum, Gümüşlük (Çerçi & Koçak, 2017).

Alydus Fabricius, 1803

Alydus calcaratus calcaratus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Habitat: In the herbaceous steppe, forest, scrub, forest-steppe transition zone, *Quercus* grove and roadside

Hostplants: *Astragalus* sp., *Sarothamnus scoparius*, *Pinus nigra*, *Corylus*, *Sarothamnus scoparius*, *Hordeum* sp.

Phenology and altitude: Juni, July; 885-1500m.

Distribution in Turkey: Adana, Amasya, Ankara (Çubuk, Beynam, Kızılcahamam-Soğuksu national park), Artvin, Çorum, Giresun, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri (Hoberlandt, 1955; Pehlivan, 1981; Kıyak, 1990a; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun, et al., 2010; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

Camptopus Amyot & Serville, 1843

Camptopus bifasciatus Fb., 1864

Habitat: In the vegetable field, xerophilic steppe, steppe transition zone and roadside.

Hostplants: *Cardaria draba* and weeds.

Phenology and altitude: July, 1220m

Distribution in Turkey: Amasya, Ankara (Çubuk damlake); Elazığ (Hazar lake), Giresun, Konya (Ereğli), Malatya, Tokat (Fieber, 1864; Hoberlandt, 1955; Pehlivan, 1981; Kiyak, 1990b; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun et al., 2010; Zengin & Dursun, 2019).

***Camptopus illustris* Hv., 1899**

Habitat: In the *Quercus* grove

Hostplant: *Centaurea aggregata aggregata*

Phenology and altitude: July, 1120m

Distribution in Turkey: Ağrı (Ağrı mountain), Diyarbakır, Elazığ (Hazar lake), Hakkari, Konya (Ereğli) (Kiritshenko, 1918; Seidenstücker, 1957; Pehlivan, 1981; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun et al., 2010).

***Camptopus lateralis* (Gm., 1817)**

Habitat: *Quercus* sp. grove, herbaceous steppe, shrub formation, cultivated area

Host plants: *Astragalus* sp., *Chrysanthemum* sp., *Compositae*, *Daucus carota*, *Glycina max*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Rosa* sp., *Rumex* sp., *Scrophularia* sp., *Torilis* sp.

Phenology and altitude: 1120-1900m, April, May, Juni, August

Distribution in Turkey: Amasya, Ankara (Kızılcahamam-Soğuksu national park, Çubuk damlake), Aydın, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı (Şabanözü), Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır (Karacadağ), Edirne, Elazığ-Hazar lake, Eskişehir, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkari, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa-Alaşehir, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Şanlıurfa, Uşak, Yozgat (Pehlivan, 1981; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun, et al., 2010; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Çerçi et al., 2016; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

***Camptopus tragacanthae* (Klt., 1845)**

Habitat: *Astragalus* sp., *Quercus* sp. grove, herbaceous and tragacanthic steppe.

Host plants: *Dorycnium pentatophyllum*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Astragalus* sp., *Astragalus microcephalus*, *Pinus nigra*.

Phenology and altitude: April, Juni, 925-1500m.

Distribution in Turkey: Amasya, Ankara (Çubuk damlake, Kızılcahamam-Soğuksu national park, Beynam), Bursa, Çorum, Eskişehir, Elazığ, Elazığ-Hazar lake, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Sivas, Tokat (Pehlivan, 1981; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun, et al., 2010; Fent & Japoshvili, 2013; Kiyak, 2016; Özgen et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

***Megalotomus* Fieber, 1860**

***Megalotomus ornaticeps* (Stål, 1858)**

Host plants: *Prosopis farcta*

Phenology and altitude: July, 831-895m.

Distribution in Turkey: Iğdır (Aralık, Karakoyunlu) (Dursun et al., 2010).

Namausus Stål, 1866

Namausus sordidatus (Stål, 1858)

Host plants: *Olea oleaster*.

Phenology and altitude: May, November, 30-270m.

Distribution in Turkey: Adana (Kozan), Mersin(Erdemli) (Dursun et al., 2010).

CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to evaluate the host plant and habitat preferences in Turkish populations of Alydidae, which are phtophagous.

For Alydidae species, the role of the host plant as a determinant of habitat quality and distribution patterns is not clear enough.

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